

Managerial Competence of Principals in the Development of Teacher Professional Competencies: Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: School principals play an important role in improving teachers' professional competence. This affects the quality of learning produced in the classroom. The purpose of this literature review is to test and analyze the managerial competence of school principals in developing teacher professional competencies. The method in this study was carried out by reviewing related articles about teacher professional competence. The research sample focused on the Google Scholar search engine with teacher professional competence as the main research. The results of the article review show that the managerial ability of the principal is very influential on the development of teacher professional competence. Therefore, the development of teachers' professional competence requires effective and efficient managerial competence of school principals.

KEYWORDS: Managerial Principal, Professional Teacher

INTRODUCTION

School principals are needed in improving teacher competence to become professionals. According to Siti Qoimah (2023) as an education leader in schools, school principals have full responsibility to develop and distribute all school resources for the benefit of education. The success of an education does not only come from teachers, but is also influenced by the presence of the principal as a leader in a school. One of the keys to success in learning is the role of the principal in managing the school. The principal is an important aspect in the development of school management, because it is directly related to efforts to plan, implement, monitor, supervise, evaluate activities, and foster working relationships in the school. According to Asha (2019) school principals have a very big role in improving all human resources, triggering a harmonious spirit of work and cooperation, interest in the development of the world of education, developing the professional quality of teachers including determining the quality patterns of the students they lead.

According to Asha (2019) the success of the principal in carrying out his duties depends on his management. The effectiveness of school management and coaching activities is closely related to the effectiveness of school personal work. If the principal is able to mobilize, guide and direct the personnel appropriately, it will undoubtedly be able to bring the school to optimal success. This is because the principal as a leader in the implementation of education needs to understand the learning process and carry out his duties well. According to Karweti (2010), the principal's managerial ability is a set of technical skills in carrying out duties as a school manager to utilize all available resources to achieve school goals effectively and efficiently. The principal's managerial competence starts from preparing school program plans, developing school organizations, and utilizing school resources so that they can carry out supervision of school activities in accordance with applicable supervisory standards. The principal as a manager has a major role in determining the management of school management because the success or failure of school goals can be influenced by how the principal carries out management functions. Juliantoro (2017) these management functions are, planning, organizing, implementing, supervising and evaluating. The Principal as a manager plays a role in managing the educational resources owned. The headmaster must be able to bring change to the school he leads into a quality school by utilizing all resources, especially teachers.

In order to educate students, teacher professionalism is very important to be the basic principle that underlies the core activities of educational institutions, namely the learning process. However, the low quality of teachers is one of the main problems in the world of education. According to Ahmad (2023), teachers are important components and resources that must be fostered and developed continuously. The form of coaching in question starts from pre-service, professional teachers to office. Therefore, not all teachers have a high level of professionalism, so it is important to first look at the aspects of competence possessed. Teacher competence is a set of mastery abilities that must exist in oneself in order to realize their performance appropriately and effectively. According to Kunandar (2011) teacher competencies include intellectual competence, physical competence, personal competence and social

competence. A teacher is defined as having competence if he is able to teach his students well. The basic competence is a description of what a person can do at work, as well as what form the work can see. Professional teachers are teachers who have the competencies required to perform educational and teaching tasks.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Managerial Principal

The headmaster has a significant role and obligation in managing his school as a manager. The ability of the principal as a school leader to carry out the responsibilities and role of a manager cannot be separated from his ability to manage his school (Nurhaco 2021). According to Kasidah (2017), the principal's competencies are "Personality competence, managerial competence, entrepreneurial competence, supervision competence, and social competence. Sohiron (2015) The principal's competence is all the skills or abilities of the principal to lead and carry out his duties and responsibilities well and understand the school as a complex and unique organization.

The relevance of managerial coaching for school managers in order to achieve successful and effective educational goals in schools, the education management process plays an important role. After all, schooling is a system with many components and various activities that must be controlled effectively and systematically. Without the support of good management processes, schools can only achieve chaotic organizational speed, which will never effectively achieve educational goals. Nurhaco (2021) therefore, every educational activity in schools requires clear and realistic planning, effective and efficient organization, mobilization and incentives of all school workers to continuously improve the quality of their performance, and continuous supervision. According to Akdon (2002) stated that managerial ability is a set of technical skills in carrying out duties as a school manager to utilize all available resources to achieve school goals effectively and efficiently.

2.2 Professional Competence of Teachers

According to Hasanah (2012), competence is a complete unity that describes the potential, knowledge, skills, and attitudes assessed, which are related to certain professions with regard to parts that can be actualized and referred to in the form of actions or performance to carry out certain professions. Nurhadi (2017) explained that teacher competency standards are developed as a whole from 4 main competencies, namely: 1. Pedagogic competence; 2. Personality; 3. Social; and 4. Professional. These four competencies are integrated in teacher performance. Professional competence is the ability to master learning materials broadly and deeply that allows guiding learners to meet the competency standards set in national standards of education. Rivayanti (2020) Teacher professional development is an effort made to advance and improve the quality and efficiency of work of all different personnel in the school environment, both educational and administrative personnel. Professional competence is the teacher's basic ability in knowledge of learning and human behavior, the field of study he fosters, the right attitude about the environment and having skills in teaching techniques. The success of teachers in carrying out their profession is largely determined by the four with an emphasis on teaching ability.

METHOD

This literature review focuses on the effect of principal supervision on teacher performance. The review process begins using Google Scholar, with the keyword, "Principal's Managerial Competence in Teacher Professional Competency Development". Article criteria that can be included in this study such as referring to keywords and the range of research years between 2015 - 2023.

Author & Year	Title	Method	Sample	Results
Asha (2019)	Principal's Managerial Steps in Improving the Competence of Islamic Teachers in Madrasah Aliyah	Qualitative	Islamic Religious Education Teacher	First, the Principal's Management in improving the competence of Islamic education teachers. Second, the application of the principal's management in improving teacher competence greatly affects the competence of PAI teachers at MAM

	Muhammadiyah Curup			Curup, namely that teachers have implemented the five basic competency standards regulated by the government as well as possible. Third, obstacles and solutions for school principal management in developing the competence of Islamic education teachers at MAM Curup, namely: The role of parents has not been seen in the person/character of each student, then the concomitant time of teaching teachers with training time in improving teacher competence
Siti Qoimah (2023)	The Role of Principal's Managerial Competence in Improving Teacher Professionalism at MTs SA Miftahul Hikmah Sukorejo Parengan	Qualitative	20 Teacher	The role of the principal in improving the professionalism of MTs SA Miftahul Hikmah Sukorejo Parengan teachers is: a) Carrying out work together and establishing good communication with stakeholders in planning, implementing, supervising, and evaluating existing programs in the school, b) Rewarding teachers who have a good work plan in management, responsibility and concern for the school in the form of salary increases; c) Holding refreshes or holidays once every year to motivate teachers; d) Maintain the reputation of the school; e) All problems are solved familiarly; f) Cultivating top-down bottom up communication methods.
Rahman Tanjung (2021)	Principal's Managerial Competence in Improving the Performance of Primary School Teachers	Qualitative	Primary School Teacher	competence of the Principal in improving the performance of elementary school teachers, namely in planning The principal makes an annual school work plan (RKTS) which concerns 8 educational standards, provides SKP criteria (employee performance targets)
Mikyal Oktarina (2019)	Principal's Managerial Competence in Improving Teacher Professionalism	Qualitative	25 Teacher	(1) The principal of SMA Negeri 1 Panga has the ability to mobilize staff, teachers and employees, optimize school resources and have the capacity to guide students, and be able to set a good teaching example. (2) The principal in improving teacher professionalism has a democratic style, increases professionalism and is happy

				to accept suggestions and criticisms from subordinates and communicate policies and problems together. (3) Obstacles of school principals in managerial implementation to improve teacher professionalism in the form of insufficient teachers and still lack of facilities and infrastructure to support the smooth running of the education process.
Asmui (2019)	The Role of Principal's Managerial Competence in Improving Teacher Professionalism	Qualitative	20 Teacher	1) The role of the principal at MA Darussholihin Kalijaga , 2) An overview of improving teacher professionalism at MA Darussholihin Kalijaga, 3) The role of the principal in improving teacher professionalism at MA Darussholihin Kalijaga.
Habibi (2015)	The influence of the principal's managerial competence and teacher work motivation on the professionalism of teachers of SMK Bismen in Tegal City	Quantitative	172 Teacher	The results of the analysis showed that the influence of the two variables simultaneously affected teacher professionalism with the coefficient of determination was 47.8%.
Choirotul Nurul Mustaqimah (2022)	Managerial Competence of School Principals and Quality Culture towards the Professionalism of Junior High School Teachers in Rembang District, Rembang Regency	Quantitative	138 Teacher	there is an influence of the principal's managerial competence on teacher professionalism
Yeni Puspitasari (2021)	The influence of principal management and teacher professionalism on teacher performance	Quantitative	76 Teacher	(1) the principal's management affects the performance of teachers in SD Negeri Tanjung Raja District; (2) teacher professionalism has no effect on teacher performance in SD Negeri Tanjung Raja District; (3) school management and teacher professionalism together do not affect teacher performance at SD Negeri Tanjung Raja.

Munawaroh (2017)	Managerial Competence of School Principals in Improving Teacher Professionalism at Sdn Blitar, Sukorejo District, Blitar City	Qualitative	20 Teacher	1) Principal planning, including: planning to supervise, training, workshops, planning on effective improvement techniques carried out with emphasis on the quality of learning and student achievement. 2) Implementation is to create a conducive school climate by providing advice and examples. 3) Evaluation includes: observing classroom activities, reviewing teaching plans and notes in class. Expand the number of people involved in the evaluation.
Deni Susana (2022)	The influence of the principal's managerial skills and teachers' work discipline on competence Profesional Guru Smp Negeri Sub Rayon 02 Kabupaten Demak	Quatitative	Teacher of SMP Negeri Sub Rayon 02 Demak Regency	there is a correlation between the principal's managerial ability and the professional competence of teachers
Saifullah (2016)	Managerial Competence of School Principals in Improving the Professional Ability of Teachers at SMA Negeri 2 Pulo Aceh Aceh Besar	Qualitative	23 Teacher	(1) The principal of SMA Negeri 2 Pulo Aceh has the ability to mobilize staff, teachers, and employees, optimize school resources, and have the capacity to guide students, and be able to set a good teaching example. (2) The principal in improving the implementation of teachers' professional abilities, improving professionals and happy to receive suggestions and criticisms from subordinates, as well as communicating policies and problems together, and (3) Obstacles of the principal in managerial implementation to improve teachers' professional abilities in the form of: insufficient teachers and still lack of facilities and infrastructure to support the smooth running of the education process.
Muhammad Darwisy Al M (2021)	Managerial Competence of School Principals in Improving Teacher Professionalism	Qualitative	Teacher	(1) The implementation of leadership applied by the principal adheres to three basic patterns, namely planning, development, and evaluation. (2) Factors that influence the principal's

				leadership in improving teacher professionalism based on internal and external factors. (3) The leadership style applied by the principal is a democratic leadership style.
Ika Ariyanti (2019)	The influence of the principal's managerial competence and organizational climate on the professionalism of public elementary school teachers in Tenganan District, Semarang Regency	Quantitative	146 Teacher	(1) there is a positive influence of the principal's managerial competence on teacher professionalism by 35.6%, (2) there is a positive influence of the organizational climate on teacher professionalism by 4.8%, and (3) there is a positive influence on the principal's managerial competence and organizational climate together on teacher professionalism by 35.2%
Suardana I Putu (2018)	The contribution of the principal's leadership style, professional competence, and managerial competence to teacher motivation (study of teacher perceptions of Sman 1 Mengwi)	Quantitative	70 Person	Based on these findings, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the leadership style, professional competence and managerial competence of the principal on the work motivation of SMA Negeri 1 Mengwi teachers separately or simultaneously

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the literature review obtained, the analysis shows that most of the articles focus on the impact of the principal's managerial competence on the professional competence of teachers. It can be seen from the review article that most of the principal's managerial competencies have a major influence in improving the professional competence of teachers. Many factors that hinder the implementation of teacher professional competency development are: 1) Supporting facilities and infrastructure in the development of teacher professional competence; 2) Limited financing capacity; 3) Motivation from teachers who have not been maximized. Based on this, in the implementation of teacher professional competency development what is needed is a work system based on the principle of togetherness, providing space for teachers in self-development, making meetings aimed at developing teacher professional competencies.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis that has been done. It can be concluded that the managerial competence of the principal is an important aspect in the development of teacher professional competence. So further research or study is needed on other aspects as reference material and input for schools and principals to support the development of teacher professional abilities.

LIMITATIONS AND ADVANCED STUDY

The weakness in this study is that this study only discusses the managerial competence of school principals in one aspect, namely the professional competence of teachers. So further research or study is needed on other aspects as reference material and input for schools and principals to support the development of teacher professional abilities.

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